

The Innovation of the Disaster Response Programme Hope Arises Again Intact (Duta Hatiiku) in Improving Post-Disaster Administrative Services in Sidoarjo District**Susi Ratnawati**

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ABSTRACT: Population administration services are very important basic needs, especially for people affected by disasters and often lose important documents. In emergency conditions, a service system that is fast, adaptive, and able to reach affected residents directly is needed. The Hatiku Ambassador innovation is a strategic step taken by the Sidoarjo Disdukcapil to ensure the fulfilment of population administration rights in a timely and direct manner in disaster-affected locations. This study aims to analyse the role of the Hatiku Ambassador innovation in optimising the post-disaster population administration service response and identify the supporting and inhibiting factors for its implementation in Sidoarjo Regency. The method used is descriptive qualitative with data collection techniques through interviews and documentation. Informants in this study included the Head of the Data Utilisation and Service Innovation Division, the Hatiku Ambassador team, the IT Section, SIAK operators, and service users. The results showed that this innovation was able to accelerate the process of issuing lost or damaged population documents within 1-2 days, and improve service access for affected residents. Successful implementation is supported by leadership commitment, human resources and infrastructure, community participation, and cross-agency collaboration. The main obstacles include budget constraints, logistics, and difficult-to-reach terrain.

KEYWORDS: Innovation; My Heart Ambassador; Population; Post-disaster

INTRODUCTION

Innovation is the development of a new tool, object, or concept that has not been used before and is intended to be something interesting and practical (Azhari et al., 2023). In addition, innovations usually materialise as new or improved goods and services, or scientific discoveries that may prove profitable in the future. A company's ability to launch significantly improved or new services is referred to as service innovation performance. To maintain competitiveness, improve service quality, and function effectively and efficiently in changing markets, public organisations must innovate (Haqie et al., 2020).

In the context of public services, innovation plays an important role in improving services in the field of population administration to the community. Innovation is created for ease of access to all needs in public services (Musaddad et al., 2020). One of the growing forms of innovation is the concept of jemput bola, which is a proactive approach in providing direct services to the community, especially in emergency situations or in hard-to-reach areas (Solong & Muliadi, 2020). This innovation has grown in importance in the field of population administration related to vital documents such as birth certificates, family cards (KK), and identity cards (KTP) (Saputra & Widiyarta, 2021). The implementation of population administration policies, standards, processes, and systems by the government is based on Law Number 24 of 2013 concerning amendments to Law Number 23 of 2006 concerning Population Administration (Male, 2023). This responsibility encourages regions to innovate in keeping services running, even in the midst of crisis conditions. One of the regions facing this challenge is Sidoarjo Regency, which has a high level of vulnerability to various types of disasters (Mala, 2021).

Sidoarjo Regency is vulnerable to various types of disasters, both caused by natural and non-natural factors (Rahmadani, 2024). The region often experiences flooding due to high rainfall and coastal areas, fires in dense settlements, tornadoes and strong winds, and the impact of non-natural disasters such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Laveda et al., 2024). These disasters have a significant impact on people's lives, including the loss of legal identity documents that are needed to access basic services such as health, education and social assistance. Without these documents, people find it difficult to get the assistance or recovery they need. Therefore, an innovative and efficient solution is needed to assist communities in retrieving lost or damaged documents due to disasters (Arfani, 2022).

One concrete form of this strategy is the Hatiku Ambassador innovation, which is specifically designed to facilitate post-disaster administrative services. The Hatiku Ambassador innovation includes the utilisation of technology to facilitate services, training for Sidoarjo District Population and Civil Registration Office officers to improve their direct service skills, and cooperation with various parties, such as the

Regional Disaster Management Agency (Rahmawati & Choiriyah, 2024).

In emergency situations, access to fast and efficient administrative services is an urgent need. The loss of civil registration documents can cause difficulties, from obstructing access to health and education services to delays in the disbursement of social assistance (Rahmawati et al., 2018). If not addressed immediately, disaster-affected communities may experience long-term difficulties in fulfilling their needs. Therefore, innovation in population administration services is very important so that the recovery of affected communities can take place quickly and effectively. With a ball-picking approach, Dukcapil can ensure that population services continue to run even in crisis conditions (Setiawan et al., 2024).

The Heart Ambassador innovation aims to accelerate population administration services for disaster-affected communities and is implemented through several strategic stages, namely identification of affected locations, data collection of disaster victims, ball pick-up services, and distribution of new documents (Yasah & Tukiman, 2025). Dukcapil worked with local governments to collect data on people who had lost their documents, and provided services directly in the affected locations. Processed documents were distributed without the need for residents to come to the Dukcapil office. Through this approach, services are faster, more efficient and responsive, helping people to restore their civil registration and speed up their return to normal life (Tasman, 2025).

This innovation has significantly contributed to increasing the accessibility of population services, especially for disaster-affected communities. With the ball pick-up service, the document recovery process becomes faster, so that people do not experience administrative obstacles in obtaining assistance and other public services (Tjahjani & Andahara, 2020). This innovation not only focuses on accelerating document replacement, but also seeks to provide education and information to citizens about the importance of population administration in post-disaster recovery. In the long term, this innovation can help create a population administration system that is more responsive, responsive and inclusive for the entire community. The purpose of this study is to analyse the role of the Sidoarjo District Disdukcapil innovation in optimising the response to post-disaster population administration services in Sidoarjo District, identifying factors that influence the optimisation of the implementation of the My Heart Ambassador innovation (Salsabella & Tukiman, 2025).

RESEARCH METHODS

In this study, the method used is a descriptive research method with a qualitative approach. This method aims to explain the phenomena, facts, or relationships between the variables studied systematically and accurately (Sarosa, 2021). Descriptive qualitative research allows researchers to explore in-depth information about the role of Dukcapil innovations in post-disaster administrative services in Sidoarjo Regency. With this approach, the research does not focus on numerical data, but on an in-depth understanding of the conditions that occur in the field.

Qualitative research requires a variety of methods in data collection to obtain a clear and in-depth picture of the problems studied. In this study, the technique used was purposive sampling, which is the selection of informants based on specific objectives relevant to the research topic (Fadli, 2021).

The analysis method used in this research refers to the interactive analysis model of Miles, Huberman and Sadana (Hashimov, 2015), which consists of three main stages:

1. Data Reduction

Data reduction is the initial process in analysing data, where researchers filter, summarise, and group data into certain themes, and eliminate irrelevant information.

2. Data Presentation (Data Display)

After the data has been reduced, the next step is to compile and present relevant data in the form of descriptive or visual narratives.

3. Conclusion Drawing and Verification

The final step is to draw conclusions based on the data that has been analysed. This conclusion is the answer to the formulation of the research problem.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

My Heart Ambassador Innovation in Optimising the Response to Post-Disaster Population Administration Services in Sidoarjo Regency

1. Improving the Speed and Responsiveness of Post-Disaster Services

The birth of the My Heart Ambassador innovation is a strategic response to the community's urgent need for population administration services in post-disaster emergency situations. During disasters such as floods and fires, residents often lose important documents such as ID cards, family cards and birth certificates, which are the main requirements for accessing social assistance, education and other public services. This condition creates an urgency for the Sidoarjo District Disdukcapil to provide emergency services that are fast, efficient, and reach directly to affected communities. My Heart Ambassador is a concrete form of social-administrative innovation regarding services as a form of state presence in crisis.

In its implementation, the Hatiku Ambassador Innovation has proven to be able to significantly accelerate the recovery of population administration documents after a disaster. The ball pick-up approach carried out directly at the affected location allows the service process, which usually takes days or even weeks, to be completed in just a matter of hours or days. Through an out-of-office service approach based on ball pick-up, the Hatiku Ambassador team goes directly to locations affected by disasters or calamities. This innovation answers the needs in the field for services that are not bureaucratic, not rigid, and able to reach residents without them having to access service offices. The service process proves that the bureaucratic system can be flexible when human values are put forward.

2. Improving Service Accessibility and Affordability

This innovation not only accelerates the process of population administration recovery, but also provides services that are more accessible, efficient, and humane. When the post-disaster situation places residents in limited conditions, the Hatiku Ambassador is directly present in their

midst.

The presence of the Hatiku Ambassador service not only resolves administrative issues, but also helps ensure the continuation of residents' basic rights, such as access to the health sector. In addition, the ease of service is also an important note for the community. Duta Hatiku not only prioritises speed, but also pays attention to the principles of ease and affordability of services without making it difficult for citizens in emergency conditions. That this innovation is not just an administrative response, but part of a social recovery strategy after disasters and calamities that favours the real needs of the community.

Factors Influencing the Optimisation of My Heart Ambassador Innovation.

1. Internal Factors

a. Leadership and Commitment

The successful implementation of the DUTA HATIKU innovation in Sidoarjo District cannot be separated from the important role of leadership and strong commitment shown by the leadership of the Population and Civil Registration Office. In post-disaster emergencies, the presence of leaders who are responsive, progressive and willing to be directly involved determines the direction and effectiveness of innovations in the field. The Head of PDIP Dukcapil revealed that the leadership showed commitment not only through direction and moral support, but also through concrete actions, such as issuing a Decree (SK) DUTA HATIKU as a strong operational legal basis. That the leadership's commitment is not symbolic, but is actually transformed into structural and operational support that strengthens the spirit of public services in disaster situations.

b. Human Resources and Infrastructure

The availability of competent human resources and adequate facilities and infrastructure are vital components in supporting the optimisation of the implementation of the Hatiku Ambassador innovation, especially in the context of post-disaster population administration services. In the midst of conditions that are full of limitations, clarity of work procedures and the use of appropriate technology can be the difference between slow and undirected services and fast, coordinated and efficient services.

SOP support also helps strengthen coordination between officers in the field. Signalling that the existence of SOPs is not only administrative, but really facilitates real work practices amid the challenges of disaster conditions. From the service recipient side, the community also felt the direct impact of the arrival of the Hatiku Ambassador team with the existence of this SOP and technology. That the readiness of human resources who understand SOPs and are supported by portable technology can create responsive, coordinated, and humane public services in the midst of emergency situations.

2. External Factors

a. Stakeholder and Local Government Cooperation

In implementing post-disaster population administration service innovations through the My Heart Ambassador programme, support from external stakeholders such as the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) and village officials plays a very important role. This cross-sector collaboration is not only administrative, but also technical and operational, which directly determines the speed and reach of services in the field.

This synergy between Dukcapil, BPBD, and village officials strengthens the effectiveness of the DUTA HATIKU programme in the field. Their support allows this innovation to reach disaster-affected residents more quickly and efficiently, while demonstrating the commitment between agencies in providing responsive and sustainable public services, even in emergency conditions.

c. Community Response and Participation

Community response and participation are important components in the successful implementation of the DUTA HATIKU innovation in the midst of post-disaster conditions. The presence of the population administration service team that proactively reached the affected locations was not only welcomed by the community, but also led to forms of active participation, not only from disaster victims, but from local residents as well, that high enthusiasm from the community still requires assistance so that the service process runs effectively. Even in some cases, residents volunteered to help with the administrative process, as conveyed by the DUTA HATIKU Team. This indicates that the presence of the ball pick-up service innovation is not only felt passively, but also encourages direct community involvement. This active participation is a reflection that the DUTA HATIKU innovation not only answers administrative needs, but also builds social closeness and a sense of belonging to public services that are responsive and present at critical times.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research that has been conducted on the Role of Dukcapil Innovations in Optimising Post-Disaster Population Administration Service Response in Sidoarjo Regency, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. My Heart Ambassador Innovation in Optimising the Response to Post-Disaster Population Administration Services.

The Hatiku Ambassador innovation has proven to make a major contribution in accelerating and facilitating post-disaster population administration services. This innovation is able to reach affected communities directly through ball pick-up services at disaster sites and refugee camps. Population documents that are lost or burned can be reissued in a relatively short time, namely 1-2 days after the incident. And in about 2 hours all documents have been reissued. In addition, the community also felt very helpful because there was no need to come to the Dukcapil office, saving costs, time and energy.

2. Factors Influencing Optimisation of My Heart Ambassador Innovation.

Internally, successful programme implementation is supported by responsive leadership, high commitment from Dukcapil leaders, readiness of human resources, availability of infrastructure, and orderly implementation of SOPs. Regular training is also an important support in improving the capacity of field officers. Externally, support from stakeholders such as BPBD, village officials and sub-district heads has been shown to accelerate the process of coordination and mobilisation of services. Local governments also play an important role in supporting programme integration in disaster management. The community's response was also quite high, as evidenced by their enthusiasm in processing documents and

cooperation during the service process. Although there were still some people who did not fully understand the flow of services, the humanist approach by officers succeeded in building trust and increasing participation.

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